

Applications of polychelates of 4-substituted benzophenone based resins with 'd' and 'f' block elements[†]

M. M. Patel, M. A. Kapadia and J. D. Joshi*

Department of Chemistry, Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidyanagar-388 120, Gujarat, India

E-mail : jdjoshi314@gmail.com

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1. Introduction

The interaction between metal ion and polymeric ligands lead to the formation of coordination polymers, in which the chelated metal ions are bounded through ligand molecules¹. Coordination polymer possesses a combination of physical properties of an organic polymer and chemical properties of the attached metal ion. Coordination compounds have advantages over organic compounds, because metals have a variety of coordination geometries and a wide range of physical properties.

The first study on polymers including metal has been carried out by Arimoto and Haven in 1955². They have been synthesized vinyl ferrocene by free radical polymerization. Recently, several coordination polymers have been prepared from aromatic and aliphatic polymers containing pendant functional groups which act as a chelat-

ing group in binding polyvalent metal ions³. Chelating polymeric ligands have more interest, due to their applications in bioinorganic industry, water purification and selective removal of waste materials in nuclear plants⁴⁻⁶, pollution control⁷, selective removal of metal from dilute solutions^{8,9}, as protective coatings on metal surfaces or as a priming layer, coating on paper, fiber and fabrics, selective binding of enzymes^{10,11}. The chelates of phenols and its derivatives possess excellent microbial activities like growth inhibition and acceleration. The investigation revealed that the antimicrobial activity of polychelates considerably increases. This is due to; chelation reduces the polarity of the metal ion by partial sharing of its positive charge with the donor groups¹². Polychelates are a novel type of substances possessing a combination of physical properties of a polymer and chemical properties

[†]Dedicated to Professor Suresh C. Ameta on his 60th birthday.

of the attached metal. The study of the antimicrobial activity has great significance, because there is a wide biological and clinical aspects of lanthanide chelates¹³. Polychelates can be used as a biocidal coating and are widely used as antifouling paints¹⁴.

Structural data of *d*-block elements dominating in the area of coordination polymers; therefore, *4f*-block elements are very interesting for the study. With the help of this study it is easy to establish relationship between their behaviour, geometry and applications. The fascinating varieties in the coordination geometry along with special properties (*f*-*f* electronic transitions) of the lanthanides have attracted the attention of researchers, resulting in many new compounds¹⁵. The addition of lanthanides to polymeric networks is of considerable interest for scientific and technological purposes¹⁶.

Selection or design of a ligand containing features such as flexibility, versatile binding modes and the ability to form hydrogen bonds is crucial to the construction of polymeric complexes¹⁵. Phenolic resin with pendant hydroxyl groups and carbonyl oxygen as donor sites yield metal coordinated polymers with interesting properties. Lanthanide ions are subject of increasing interest in coordination chemistry. A sustained research activity has been devoted to lanthanide complexes, because of their variable coordination number, in the range of 3 to 12¹⁷, which will make lanthanide ions become excellent spacers in assembling fascinating framework.

Many organic reactions are induced or catalyzed by Lewis acids, *4f*-block elements and/or its compounds can serve as a "reservoir" of Lewis acidity of different strength and size, which becomes very useful and interesting. It is very interesting to study the role of *4f*-block elements and its compounds as catalysts for organic synthesis. According to HSAB classification given by Pearson¹⁸, lanthanides are considered as hard acids.

Organic polymers have got limitations, when organic polymers exposed to the atmosphere or used as adhesives, coatings and in the field of biomedical science, polymers may get contaminated or infected by microorganisms such as bacteria. Microorganisms have been found to be the cause for disbonding and blistering of protective coatings in various service situations. Some report indicates the presence of a large number of microorganisms in area where coatings have been deteriorated. Coating material itself can be infected by microorganisms from outside and bring about the deterioration in such a way that the physical reactions leading to disbonding and blis-

tering can take place¹⁹. These problems can be solved by the addition of metal ions in the polymeric system²⁰, which changes the physicochemical as well as biological properties of the polymers²¹. Metal containing monomeric and polymeric materials with antibacterial activity have been patented²².

Metal-containing polymers represent a broad classification of polymers with inorganic salt groups attached to the polymer chain. They are generally referred as 'poly-electrolytes' when they have sufficient ionic charge to be soluble in water and as 'ionomers' when the concentration of ion-containing groups is too low for water solubility. Unlike homogeneous polymer systems, polymers containing ionic group interact to form ion rich aggregates contained in the non-polar polymer matrix. The resulting interactions strongly influence polymer properties and applications. This is an attractive area of applied research and development. Polymers having metal linkages in the backbone are of interest in the scientific and industrial area. They have various applications in material science including in the biomedical fields²³⁻³³. These polymers have a wide variety of properties that lead to different applications as aqueous thickeners, impregnants, textile sizers, adhesives, additives^{25,34}, resins³⁵⁻³⁷, catalysts³⁸.

The aim of this review is to focus on methods of synthesis, properties and applications of metal-containing polychelates of benzophenone based resins.

2. Benzophenone based resins

Benzophenone based resins (BPBR) possess excellent mechanical and physical properties, UV absorption, high thermal stability, metal sorption capacity³⁹⁻⁴¹ etc. Modification of BPBR by incorporating metal and functional groups are used extensively to improve various typically desired properties of material, such as enhanced thermal stability, flexibility and solubility. These properties lead to variety of applications. Metal-containing BPBR, in which the metal is firmly incorporated into the backbone of the polymer chain, can be prepared by the reaction between diols, formaldehyde and metal acetates or nitrates.

Although the condensation of phenol and formaldehyde is one of the most well-known reaction route to synthesize chelating polymers⁴²⁻⁴⁵. An interesting feature of these condensation reactions is, the variation in the properties of the resulting polymers under different reaction conditions.

The nature of the intervening spacer groups connect-

ing the active chelating ligands in chelating polymers, plays an important role in the chelation process⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸. In phenol-formaldehyde polymers, the chelate-forming phenolic moieties are linked by methylene groups (-CH₂-). To change these linkages, one may use the more versatile condensation reaction^{49,50}, in which a phenolic compound is condensed with primary or secondary diols.

2.1. Synthesis of 4-substituted benzophenone derivatives :

Recently, aromatic and aliphatic polymers containing pendant functional groups which act as chelating group in binding polyvalent metal ions are more attractive. Because the pendant chelating groups are able to form coordinated covalent bond with metal ion to set the metal ion in the backbone of the polymeric material in the acceptable environment.

In case of 2,4-dihydroxybenzophenone the substitution at 4th position can be made by selective *O*-alkylation on phenolic -OH group by using methyl iodide, 1-bromo ethane, 1-bromo butane etc. to synthesize 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy benzophenone, 2-hydroxy-4-ethoxy benzophenone and 2-hydroxy-4-butoxy benzophenone.

While 2-hydroxy-4-methacryloyloxy benzophenone can be synthesized by reaction of 2,4-dihydroxybenzophenone, triethylamine, hydroquinone, 2-butanone and methacryloyl chloride at room temperature.

2.2. Benzophenone-formaldehyde resin :

To prepare 2,4-dihydroxybenzophenone-formaldehyde resin the condensation of 2,4-dihydroxybenzophenone, S. Trioxane and P-TSA (*p*-toluene sulphonic acid) was carried out at 100 °C for 12 h. Then the reaction mixture was separated, washed with water and purified by dissolving it into DMF. To the filtrate excess of sodium chloride was added with constant stirring. The resin reappears was dried at suitable temperature.

In a similar manner 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzophenone-formaldehyde, 2-hydroxy-4-ethoxybenzophenone-formaldehyde and 2-hydroxy-4-butoxybenzophenone-formaldehyde resins can be synthesized.

2.3. Benzophenone-diol resins :

The synthesis of benzophenone-diol resins, benzophenone derivative and respective diol was condensed in presence of acid catalyst at suitable constant temperature. This condensation allows copolymerization between the phenolic moiety and respective diol. This led to form benzophenone-diol resin. Thus synthesized resin was separated by filtration and properly washed with water fol-

lowed by ethanol to remove excess of acid and unreacted starting material. It was further purified by dissolving it into dimethyl formamide, which reappears in water. This procedure was repeated for several times.

To synthesize 2,4-dihydroxybenzophenone-diol resins³, condensation of 2,4-dihydroxybenzophenone with ethane diol, 1,2-propylene glycol, 1,3-propanediol, 1,3-butane-diol and 1,4-butanediol was carried out. In a similar manner condensation of 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzophenone with ethanediol, 1,2-propyleneglycol, 1,3-propanediol, 1,3-butanediol and 1,4-butanediol was carried out to get 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzophenone-diol resins^{39,40}.

Using same procedure 2-hydroxy-4-butoxybenzophenone-diol resins were prepared⁴¹.

2.4. 4-Methacryloxy benzophenone resins :

Kalliyappan *et al.*⁵¹ have synthesized poly(2-hydroxy-4-methacryloyloxy benzophenone) by condensation of 2-hydroxy-4-methacryloyloxy benzophenone, 2-butanone and benzoyl peroxide in nitrogen atmosphere at 70 °C for 8 h. The content was then washed with methanol and purified by dissolving it into dimethyl formamide and reappearing in water for several times.

In this resin methacryloyl group is attached with the oxygen atom of phenolic -OH group (Fig. 1), which is polymerized to give polymer. Here also the chelate forming groups (>C=O and -OH) are being able to form coordination covalent bond with metal ions and sets metal ion into the polymeric backbone. In this case methacryloyl group is getting polymerized while in benzophenone-formaldehyde and benzophenone-diol resins benzophenone moiety itself get polymerized at 3 and 5 positions.

Fig. 1. Poly(2-hydroxy-4-methacryloyloxy benzophenone).

3. Synthesis of polychelates

Polychelate is a coordination polymer in which a metal ion is coordinated with an organic moiety, in polychelate there is a metal atom or ion for each monomer unit⁵²⁻⁵⁴

polychelates possess square planer geometry.

where, $M = Ni^{II}, Co^{II}$ and Zn^{II}

$X = H_2O$

$R = H, CH_3, C_4H_9$

Fig. 2. Proposed geometry of the polychelates.

Kalliyappan *et al.*⁵¹ have synthesized polychelates of poly(2-hydroxy-4-methacryloyloxy benzophenone) with transition metal ions and studied their thermal catalytic and magnetic properties. They have dissolved the polymer in THF and adjusted the pH 7.0. Then the metal acetate solution was added dropwise with constant stirring, the obtained product was digested on water bath and then filtered. The chelation with metal ion is taking place through the oxygen of keto group and oxygen of phenolic -OH group of two different polymeric chains. The reduction of the keto group of polymeric chain was carried out by $NaBH_4$ (sodium borohydrate) and then it was chelated with metal ion. But polychelate was not obtained, thus it was confirmed that $>C=O$ group is taking part in chelation (Fig. 3). X-Ray diffraction study

where, $M = Ni^{II}$ and Cu^{II}

$X = H_2O$

Fig. 3. Proposed geometry of the polychelates.

shows that polymers are amorphous in nature where as polychelates are crystalline in nature.

3.2. Polychelates with lanthanides(III) :

The synthesis of coordination polymers containing transition metal ions has become widespread over the past decade, structural data of *d*-block elements dominating in the area of coordination polymers and very few reports on lanthanide-metal coordination polymers are available. But in recent time lanthanide elements attracting the attention of researchers, because of wide range of their coordination numbers i.e. 3 to 12. Hence lanthanides enabled to form variety of coordination compounds with different geometries. Thus lanthanide ions become excellent spacers in assembling variety of framework. Reports on lanthanide ions in polymeric systems generally involve either polymers used as matrices for lanthanide ions or complexes bounded to branches of the polymer chains. The use of lanthanide ions in the polymer backbones normally results in insoluble materials, which obtained upon dissolution.

Lanthanide polychelates of different 4-substituted benzophenone-diol resins such as 2,4-dihydroxybenzophenone-diol resins, 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzophenone-diol resins, 2-hydroxy-4-butoxybenzophenone-diol resins were prepared (Fig. 4). Hydrated acetates of lanthanum, praseodymium, neodymium, samarium, gadolinium, terbium and dysprosium were used in the synthesis of polychelates.

Synthesis of polychelates of lanthanides(III) with 4-substituted benzophenone-diol resins was carried out us-

where, $M = La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III}, Gd^{III}, Tb^{III}$ and Dy^{III}

$X = H_2O$

$R = H, CH_3, C_4H_9$

Fig. 4. Proposed structure of the polychelates.

ing similar procedure. The product formed was digested and then filtered. From the characterization it was found that, the metal-ligand ratio is 1 : 2 in all the polychelates.

It is observed that the behaviour of Ln^{III} polychelates was similar to that of transition metal polychelates⁵⁶. It is also found that two water molecules eliminated above 150 °C temperature in all the polychelates. According to Nikolaev *et al.*⁵⁷ water eliminated above 150 °C may be due to coordination with the metal ion. The nature of the water molecules observed in polymer-metal complexes is water of coordination. Due to the presence of water molecules, the proposed geometry of polychelates is octahedral. Amongst all the polychelates lanthanum(III) polychelates are found diamagnetic while rests all are paramagnetic in nature.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) study of synthesized resins and polychelates were carried out to understand the inner morphology and pore structure. The morphology of fracture surface for the resin was quite different from polychelates. The morphology of the resin shows a fringed model of the crystalline-amorphous structure. The fringes represent transition state between the crystalline and amorphous phase⁵⁸. The resin exhibits more amorphous character with closed packed surface having deep pits.

nature. Thus physico-chemical properties of resins are changed due to chelation.

Applications

4. Catalytic activity of polychelates

Transition and lanthanide metal ions are known for excellent catalytic activity. According to HSAB classification given by Pearson both are Lewis acids. So they can be used as reservoir for Lewis acidity, which is responsible for their catalytic nature.

Wang *et al.*⁵⁹ has mentioned that the polymeric support and the polymeric end groups also affect the catalytic activity and selectivity of polymer-metal complexes in hydrogenation reaction.

Kaliyappan *et al.*⁵¹ has carried out successful hydrolysis of ethyl acetate, polymerization of *N*-vinylpyrrolidone and oxidation of cyclohexanone to cyclohexanol using Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} polychelates.

Joshi *et al.*⁶⁰ have carried out the synthesis of Biginelli three component, one-pot synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones (Fig. 5) and their derivatives with different aromatic aldehydes and β-ketoesters successfully by using different polychelates. Yield obtained was between 85-90%. The important significance of this type of catalyst is that, it can be reused by giving simple water

Fig. 5. Synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones.

The pores of the resin are filled after interaction with metal ions, with polymeric ligand. This phenomenon is observed in the SEM study of polychelates. The nature of the resins and polychelates are quite different; this is due to chelation of metal ion in polymeric backbone. The surface of the polychelates is quite uniform but presence of some holes and cracks are observed, this may be due to air. The polychelates are found to be crystalline in

treatment and drying.

Many workers have reported synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones and their derivatives by using different catalysts and reaction conditions, but in all the cases, following difficulties are observed.

- Low yield⁶¹.
- More reaction time is required, i.e. more loss of energy, hence obtained product is not cheaper.

- More reactivity of catalysts (chemically harmful)^{62,63}, i.e. reaction control need special attention.
- Lack of simplicity in the reaction process⁶⁴.

Looking to the above difficulties, use of above synthesized polychelates as a catalyst in synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones and their derivatives, the following interesting results are observed, which are favourable with respect to other aspects.

- Good yield i.e. above 85–90%.
- Reaction is quite faster i.e. less time consuming reaction, amount of energy required less for the reaction. Therefore cost of the product is less.
- The nature of the catalyst is mild and non hazardous in compared to other catalysts used by various researchers^{62,63} to synthesize 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones and their derivatives.
- The used catalyst i.e. polychelate is superior; it can be recycled with normal treatment of water. The treated catalyst is equally efficient as new one.
- The catalyst is economical.
- The quality of the product obtained is very good.

5. Antimicrobial activity

5.1. Preparation of microbial culture :

The antimicrobial activity of resin and its polychelates were checked against *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and yeast strains *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. The antimicrobial effect of polychelates was investigated by standard microbiological parameters using Agar Diffusion Method⁶⁵. The concentration of the compound tested for the antimicrobial activity was 500 ppm during the experiment. The bacterial culture was maintained on *N*-agar (*N*-broth, 2.5% w/v agar). The yeast culture was maintained on MGYB in 3 % (w/v) agar.

For inoculum developments of bacterial and yeast culture, a loop of cell mass from pregrown slants was inoculated into sterile *N*-broth tubes containing 15 mL medium and incubated on a shaker at 150 rpm and 37 °C for 24 h, to obtain sufficient cell density (i.e. 1×10^8 cells/mL).

Sterile, melted *N*-agar was initially inoculated with corresponding cultures and poured into a sterile empty petri plate and allowed to solidify. A ditch was prepared with the help of a sterile scalpel on opposite ends, with one for control (solvent without compound) and the other for the test sample. For finding the minimum inhibitory

concentration, all the cultures were tested for different concentration of compound ranging from 50–1000 ppm. Thereafter, the plates were transferred to the refrigerator for 10 min to allow the sample diffuse out from the ditch and into the agar before organisms start growing followed by incubation at 37 °C for 24 h. Next day the distance in millimeter (mm), from the ditch was measured as a parameter of inhibition.

5.2. Media composition :

For the growth and test of bacteria and yeast, the *N*-broth and MGYB media were used. The composition used is as shown below.

N-Broth Peptone 0.6% (6.0 g), NaCl 0.15% (1.5 g), beef extract 0.15% (1.5 g) were dissolved in 1 L distilled water and pH was adjusted to 6.7–7.3.

MGYP Malt extract (3.0 g), glucose (10.0 g), yeast extract (3.0 g) and peptone (5.0 g) were dissolved in 1 L distilled water and pH was adjusted to 5.5.

5.3. Antimicrobial activity of resin and polymer-metal complexes :

The polymeric ligands were found biologically active and their polymer-metal complexes showed significantly enhanced antibacterial activity against one or more bacterial species, which compared with the uncomplexed polymeric ligand. It is known that chelation tends to make the ligands act as more potent bactericidal agents, than the parent ligand. The antimicrobial activity of the compound increases after metal chelation. Chelation reduces the polarity of the central metal ion by partial sharing of its positive charge with the donor groups⁶⁶ increasing lipophilic nature of the central metal ion, which in turn favours its permeation to the lipid layer of the membrane. Other factors, viz. stability constant, molar conductivity, solubility and magnetic moment are also responsible for increasing the anti-microbial activity of the complexes⁶⁷.

6. Summary of the work

The methods of synthesis, characterization and applications of polychelates of transition and inner transition metal ions have been studied. In polychelates the metal ions are located on the side group of the resins. The results showed that the incorporation of metal ions into the polymer chain greatly influenced the mechanical, thermal and morphological properties. It is found that, metal-chelated 4-substituted benzophenones are promising ma-

terials for various applications such as, antibacterial agents for coating and catalysts. The study will be useful to develop new series of Ln^{III} polychelates and their applications in other fields.

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